

Manganese(IV) Complexes Containing Acetylacetonate and Dithiocarbamate Chelates

B. PRADHAN and D. V. RAMANA RAO

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008, Orissa

Manuscript received 27 August 1980, accepted 9 June 1981

Six neutral complexes of manganese(IV) of the type $Mn(AA)_2X_2$ (where AA is acetylacetonate, diethyl- or morpholyl dithiocarbamate, and X is chlorine or bromine) have been prepared by oxidation of $Mn(AA)_2$ by halogens in suitable media. Conductivity, infrared, uv and magnetic susceptibility measurements support a manganese(IV) formulation for the complexes.

WELL characterized complex compounds of manganese(IV) are limited. Among them are the anionic chloro, fluoro and iodato complexes¹ having the formula $[Mn^{IV}X_6]^{2-}$. Some cationic complexes²⁻⁷ of manganese(IV) have been obtained by oxidation of manganese(III) complexes by potassium permanganate, air or manganous perchlorate. Interesting intermediate products of oxidation have also been reported. When $Co(acac)_3$ was treated with bromine, $Co(acac)_3Br$ was obtained as an intermediate product⁸. Isobe and Kawaguchi⁹ obtained $Mn(acac)_2X$ as an intermediate compound by treating *tris*(acetylacetonato) manganese(III) with HX ($X = Cl, Br, I$). Hence, it was thought worthwhile to treat manganese(III) compounds with chlorine and bromine in suitable solvent media which resulted in oxidation of manganese(III) to manganese(IV). Six neutral manganese(IV) complexes are thus isolated and reported in this investigation.

Experimental

Tris-diethyl and morpholyl dithiocarbamates, and *tris*-acetylacetonate of manganese(III) were prepared by known methods¹⁰.

(i) *Bromination*: Very dilute solution of bromine in carbon disulphide was added dropwise to a solution of $Mn(et_2dtc)_3$, $Mn(morphdtc)_3$ or $Mn(acac)_3$ in the same solvent and stirred vigorously till the colour changed. The solvent was removed at 60° and the solid product washed with ether and finally dried *in vacuo*.

(ii) *Chlorination*: Dry chlorine gas was bubbled slowly through a suspension/solution of $Mn(et_2dtc)_3$, $Mn(morphdtc)_3$ or $Mn(acac)_3$ in carbon tetrachloride with constant shaking till the colour changed or solid product separated out. In case of $Mn(et_2dtc)_2Cl_2$, the resulting solution was kept at 100° for removing the excess solvent. The separated compound was washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*. In the case of $Mn(morphdtc)_2Cl_2$ and $Mn(acac)_2Cl_2$, solid products separated out

on passing Cl_2 which were filtered, washed with CCl_4 , ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Elemental analyses were carried out by standard methods and results were consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The molecular weight of the compounds was determined by Rast method indicated that the compounds are monomeric (Table 1). Molar conductance of $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution in ethanolic medium was measured by a Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CLO102 with a dip type cell. The low values of molar conductance (~ 4 mhos) indicate that they are non-ionic. The magnetic susceptibility of the solid specimens was measured at room temperature by Gouy method. Infrared spectra in the range 5000-650 cm^{-1} were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 spectrophotometer. Far infrared spectra of $Mn(et_2dtc)_2Br_2$, $Mn(et_2dtc)_2Cl_2$, $Mn(acac)_2Br_2$ and $Mn(acac)_2Cl_2$ were recorded at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, IIT, Madras. The electronic spectra of the compounds in the ethanolic solution were recorded using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and molecular weight data of the compounds are given in Table 1 and the infrared and electronic spectral bands pertaining to the compounds are presented in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

The observed magnetic moments lie between 3.91 and 4.09 B. M. (Table 1) which is within the range of values obtained for other high spin manganese(IV) (d^5) complexes¹¹ for which orbitally non-degenerate quartet ground states have been proposed. The results suggest, therefore, high-spin manganese(IV) (d^5) state for which the ground state is $^4A_{2g}$ (expected magnetic moment is 3.88 B. M. which should be temperature independent). The oxidation state of manganese in the complexes has been further determined iodometrically by reacting the compounds with acidified KI and estimating the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate solution. Each atom of manganese was found to liberate ~ 1.7 atoms of iodine.

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, MELTING POINT, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA OF MANGANESE(IV) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	m.p. (°C)	%Mn Found (Calcd.)	%Halogen Found (Calcd.)	%Sulfur Found (Calcd.)	Molar conductance (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)
1. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂ Br ₂	Greenish black	62	10.78 (10.74)	30.90 (31.26)	25.34 (25.08)	4.5	3.91	586.3 (511.3)
2. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂ Cl ₂	Shining black	110	13.85 (13.02)	16.50 (16.81)	30.52 (30.40)	4.3	4.06	403.8 (421.8)
3. Mn(morphdte) ₂ Br ₂	Dark grey	90	10.48 (10.18)	29.10 (29.63)	23.72 (23.78)	4.4	4.09	510.4 (539.2)
4. Mn(morphdte) ₂ Cl ₂	Greyish black	95	12.88 (12.20)	15.20 (15.74)	28.06 (28.47)	4.3	4.00	511.1 (450.3)
5. Mn(acac) ₂ Br ₂	Dirty green	115	13.60 (13.30)	38.22 (38.70)	—	4.3	4.06	464.8 (412.9)
6. Mn(acac) ₂ Cl ₂	Dirty brown	110	16.47 (16.95)	21.24 (21.88)	—	4.4	4.06	310.3 (324.0)

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF MANGANESE(IV) COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Compound	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu_{as}(C-S)$	$\nu(Mn-S)$	$\nu(Mn-O)$	$\nu(Mn-Cl)$	$\nu(C=O)$	$\nu(C=C)$	C-H bending
1. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂	1448s	1000s	368, 395	—	—	—	—	—
2. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂ Br ₂	1515s	1000vs	378, 398	—	—	—	—	—
3. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂ Cl ₂	1515s	1000vs	378, 398	—	285	—	—	—
4. Mn(morphdte) ₂	1498s	992s	—	—	—	—	—	—
5. Mn(morphdte) ₂ Br ₂	1530s	992s	—	—	—	—	—	—
6. Mn(morphdte) ₂ Cl ₂	1530s	992s	—	—	—	—	—	—
7. Mn(acac) ₂	—	—	—	—	—	1585s	1520s	—
8. Mn(acac) ₂ Br ₂	—	—	—	500	—	1602s	1538s	1190s
9. Mn(acac) ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	—	510	285	1602s	1538s	1190s

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF MANGANESE(IV) COMPLEXES

Compound	Absorption max. (cm ⁻¹)		
	$^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^2E_g, ^2T_{2g}$	$^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$	$^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}$
1. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂ Br ₂	16000	21740	24390
2. Mn(et ₂ dte) ₂ Cl ₂	16000	21740	24690
3. Mn(morphdte) ₂ Br ₂	16000	21740	24690
4. Mn(morphdte) ₂ Cl ₂	16180	21740	24690
5. Mn(acac) ₂ Br ₂	16000	21740	25000
6. Mn(acac) ₂ Cl ₂	16000	21980	25000

The infrared spectral data presented in Table 2 show that the $\nu(Mn-S)$ and $\nu(C=N)$ bands are shifted slightly to higher frequency ranges upon oxidation. This is consistent with the observed shortening of Mn-S and C=N bond lengths and follow the general trends already observed for other oxidised transition metal dithiocarbamate chelates^{5,12-14}. Similar observation was also reported by Brown *et al*⁶ for manganese(IV) complexes. Bidentate dithiocarbamates exhibit $\nu_{as}(CS)$ near 1000 cm⁻¹ as a single band¹⁵. The singlet band at 1000 or 992 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) due to $\nu_{as}(CS)$ indicate that the dithiocarbamates were coordinated as bidentate ligands¹⁵. The band at 285 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(Mn-Cl)$ indicates that the halogens are coordinated to the metal atom. In the case of acetylacetonate complexes the $\nu(C=O)$ and $\nu(C=C)$ bands were also found to be elevated upon oxidation (Table 2). The appearance of C-H bending frequency at 1190 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) in both the acetylacetonate complexes indicates that the ligand has not undergone halogenation¹⁶⁻¹⁸. On the other hand, the coordination of the ligands as well

as the halogens to the metal ion is indicated by the presence of $\nu(Mn-O)$ and $\nu(Mn-Cl)$ bands¹⁹ at 500 and 285 cm⁻¹, respectively. Thus, it is concluded that in these compounds the metal ion has undergone oxidation and the ligands have not been halogenated.

The electronic spectral data are given in Table 3. Manganese(IV) has the same d-electronic configuration as chromium(III). The bands of the complexes found at ~16000, ~21700 and ~24600 cm⁻¹ may be assigned²⁰ to $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^2E_g, ^2T_{2g}$, $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$ and $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}$ transitions, respectively which also indicate an octahedral environment round Mn(IV) ion.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B. P.) is thankful to the Education Department, Government of India for a research grant.

References

1. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, 'Advanced Inorganic Chemistry', Third edition, Wiley Eastern Reprint, 1976, 852.
2. P. RAY and M. RAY, *Sci. and Cult.*, 1957, **23**, 158; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 595.
3. R. L. DUTTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 32.
4. S. N. PODDAR and N. G. PODDAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **5**, 276.
5. E. A. PASEK and D. K. STRAUB, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 259.
6. K. L. BROWN, R. M. GOLDING, P. C. HEALY, K. J. JESSOP and W. C. TENNANT, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, **27**, 2075.

PRADHAN & RAMANA RAO : MANGANESE(IV) COMPLEXES CONTAINING ACETYLACETONE ETC.

7. S. N. PODDAR, D. K. BISWAS and S. N. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 83.
8. K. ISOBE, K. NODA, Y. NAKAMURA and S. KAWAGUCHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1973, **46**, 1699.
9. K. ISOBE and S. KAWAGUCHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1975, **48**, 250.
10. B. PRADHAN and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 226.
11. R. D. W. KEMMITT, 'Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry,' Vol. 3, Pergamon, Oxford, 1973, 788.
12. R. M. GOLDING, C. M. HARRIS, K. J. JESSOP and W. C. TENNANT, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, **25**, 2527.
13. P. T. BEURSKENS, J. A. CRAS and J. J. STEGGERDA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 810.
14. A. AVDEEF, J. P. FACKLER and R. G. FISCHER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 6972.
15. F. BONATI and R. UGO, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1967, **10**, 257.
16. K. NAKAMOTO, P. T. MCCARTHY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 1272.
17. C. DJORDJEVIC, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *Chem. and Ind. (London)*, 1959, 122.
18. K. UNO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1955, **59**, 998.
19. JOHN R. FERRARO, 'Low-Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds', Intenum Press, New York, 1971.
20. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier Publishing Co., 1968, 283.